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In the collection of materials of the conference, the role and role of Science, Education and production in the era of globalization, the pressing problems of the issues of interaction of these processes, feedback on their solutions were presented by mature specialists of the field.

In addition, research on the scientific and practical topic, carried out in the economics, Exact Sciences, Natural Sciences and socio-humanities during the globalization period, information is presented in the scientific and practical fields, which includes the latest innovative technologies in the fields of production.

It can be argued that this collection is one of the specific intersections of current thoughts and innovative ideas of the world of science. This scientific and practical conference was actively attended by professors and scientific researchers engaged in scientific research in Uzbekistan and foreign countries. In increasing the position of the scientific and practical conference, the professors and teachers of domestic and foreign higher educational institutions made a significant contribution.

Professors and teachers of foreign higher educational institutions who actively participated in the work of the conference made a worthy contribution to the high level of interaction with scientists of our country. The processes of international cooperation with foreign countries and exchange with them in the field of Science in the era of globalization have a positive effect on the development of Higher Education, the fields of Science and production. The materials of this conference are special in that they include a wide range of research, from theoretical developments to practical solutions, demonstrating the diversity of approaches and directions in this area.

In conclusion, it should be noted that this scientific and practical conference will be a very useful collection for everyone who is interested in modern research in the fields of further development of Higher Education, Science, Education and production in the era of globalization. The authors are responsible for the content and quality of the articles and abstracts included in the collection.

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LIMON KISLOTASINI BIOTEKNOLOGIK ISHLAB CHIQRISH

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O'ZMU Jizzax filiali "Biotexnologiya" yo'nalishi talabalari¹
O'ZMU Jizzax filiali "Biotexnologiya" kafedrasida katta o'qituvchisi²

Annotatsiya: Ushbu tezis limon kislotasining biotexnologik ishlab chiqarilishi, fizik-kimyoviy xususiyatlari, asosan oziq-ovqat va farmatsevtika sohasida qo'llanilishi haqida. Limon kislotasining fermentatsiyasiga ta'sir qiluvchi bir qancha omillar, jumladan, uglerod manbai, aeratsiya, mikroelementlar va qo'ziqorin morfologiyasi. Texnologiyalar asosan *Aspergillus niger* dan foydalanadigan qattiq yoki suyuq oziqa muhitlari asosida sanoat miqyosida olindi va *Yarrowia lipolytica* bilan olib boriladigan jarayonlar, shuningdek, mahsulotni qayta tiklash texnologiyasi ham tasvirlangan. Ishlab chiqarishda apelsin qobig'i va boshqa qo'shimcha mahsulotlarni xom ashyo sifatida ishlatishni umumlashtirildi.

Kalit so'zlar: Fermentatsiya, krips sikl, alkan, glikoliz, vododrod ioni, pirouzum kislotasi, spora, metanol.

Limon kislotasi $C_6H_8O_7$, uch asosiy oksikislotadir. Suvli eritmalaridan rangsiz shaklda, suvning bir molekulasini bilan birga, tiniq, rombik ko'rinishidagi kristallar xolatida kristallizatsiyalanadi. Limon kislotasi birinchi marta Angliyada tijorat maqsadida ishlab chiqarilgan. Limon kislotasi 1919-yilgacha, birinchi sanoat jarayoni ishlatilgan *Aspergillus niger* Belgiyada boshlangan. Limon kislotasining katta miqdorda ishlab chiqarilishiga jarayonda uglerod manbai sifatida uglevod va uglevodlardan foydalanish mumkin ekanligi tasdiqlangandan keyingina erishildi. Limon kislotasi trikarboksilik kislotadir molekulyar og'irligi 210,14g/mol hisoblanadi. Limon kislotasi birinchi marta Angliyada tijorat maqsadida ishlab chiqarilgan. Limon sharbati tijorat manbai bo'lib qoldi. Limon kislotasi 1919-yilgacha birinchi sanoat jarayoni uchun ishlatilgan *Aspergillus niger* shtammidan foydalanish Belgiyada boshlangan. Limon kislotasi glitserindan Grimoux tomonidan sintez qilingan. Limon kislotasi ishlab chiqarishda *Aspergillus awamori*, *Aspergillus nidulans* shtammidan foydalaniladi. [1.3].

Limon kislotasi *Aspergillus niger* mikroskopik zamburug'ini melassali oziq muhitida o'stirib, mikrobiologik sintez qilish asosida olinadi. Limon kislotasini ishlab chiqarish jarayoni o'zida mikrobiologik texnologiyaning barcha asosiy bosqichlarini mujassamlashtiradi:

1. Ekish materialini olish;
2. Melassa - xom-ashyolarni fermentatsiyaga tayorlash;
3. Havoni tayorlash va sterillash;
4. Fermentatsiya;
5. Mitselial zamburug' - produsentning biomassalarini ajratish;
6. Kultural suyuqlikdan limon kislotasini ajratish va uni kristall xolatga tushirish[4].

Ekuv materialini tayorlash. Maxsus mikrobiologik muzeylarda saqlanadigan *Aspergillus niger* shtamlari quruq spora ko'rinishida (konidiy) aktivlashtirilgan

ko'mir aralashmasida saqlanadi. Dastlabki kultura, probirkalarda agarli ozuqa muhitida rivojlanadi, so'ngra kolba va kyuvetalarda qattiq ozuqa muhitida o'stiriladi. Qattiq ozuqa muhitining sirtida o'stirilganda konidiya hosil qiluvchi mitselial qoplam rivojlanadi. Yetilgan konidiylar vakuum uskunasi yordamida yig'ib olinadi[4].

Xom-ashyolarni tayorlash. Limon kislotasini sanoat asosida olish uchun substrat sifatida shakar ishlab chiqarishning qoldiq mahsuloti bo'lgan melassa qabul qilingan. Melassa aniq standartga (tarkibga) ega bo'lmagan xom-ashyo hisoblanadi. Shuning uchun ham uning ishlab-chiqarishga yaroqliligi laboratoriya sharoitida kichik hajmda nazorat fermentatsiyasi o'tkazib, tekshirib ko'rilgach belgilanadi[2.4].

Fermentatsiya. Polisaxaridlar fermentatsiya uchun foydali xom ashyo hisoblanadi. Sanoatda eng ko'p ishlatiladigan uglerod manbalari fermentatsiyalari kraxmal gidrolizidan glyukoza siroplari, shakarlavlagi, shinni va past sifatli shakarqamishdir. Eng yuqori mahsuldorlikka odatda 14-22% shakar yordamida erishiladi. Amaldagi substratga ko'ra fermentatsiyaning sirt ustida va suyuqlikda o'stirish usullari mavjud. Yuzaki suyuqlik kulturalari odatda ketma-ket amalga oshiriladi, bug'doy kepagi, kartoshkadan tayyorlangan fermentatsiya bulonlari yordamida hamda kraxmal, glyukoza siroplari. Ushbu texnologiya *A. niger* shtammlaridan foydalanib amalga oshiriladi. Chunki *A. niger* genetik jihatdan ancha beqaror[3].

Limon kislotasini ajratish va uni kristall holda olish. Mitseliylar ajratilgandan so'ng kultural suyuqlik o'z tarkibida limon, glyukon va oksalat kislotalarni aralashmasi, shakar cho'kmalari va mineral aralashmalarini saqlaydi. Kultural suyuqlikdan limon kislotani ajratib olish, uning limon kislotasining uch kalsiyli tuzida kam eruvchanlik xususiyatini hosil qilishiga asoslanadi. Limon kislota eritmasi gips, kalsiy oksalat, ko'mir va og'ir metall tuzlarining qoldiqlaridan vakuum-filtr orqali ajratiladi. Filtrlangan limon kislota eritmasi bug'lantirishga yo'naltiriladi. 70°C haroratda vakuum-uskunada bug'lantirilgan eritma kristallizatorga beriladi. Hosil qilingan limon kislota kristallari sentrifugalash orqali ajratiladi va ko'p bo'lmagan miqdordagi sovuq suvda yuvilib quritishga yo'naltiriladi. Kristall holatdagi limon kislotasini quritish lentali yoki barabanli pnevmatik quritgichda, 35°C dan oshmagan haroratli havoda amalga oshiriladi. Tayor preparat tarkibida 99,5% dan kam bo'lmagan miqdordagi limon kislotasini (monogidratga hisoblaganda) saqlashi lozim[3.4].

XULOSA

Limon kislotasi biotexnologik usulda ishlab chiqarilishi ekologik xavfsiz, iqtisodiy samarali va sanoat uchun muhim jarayon hisoblanadi. Mikroorganizmlar, ayniqsa *Aspergillus niger* kabi zamburug'lar yordamida fermentatsiya orqali olinadigan limon kislotasi oziq-ovqat, farmatsevtika, kosmetika va kimyo sanoatida keng qo'llaniladi. Zamonaviy biotexnologik yondashuvlar ishlab chiqarish samaradorligini oshirib, chiqindisiz va barqaror texnologiyalarni rivojlantirishga xizmat qiladi. Bu esa limon kislotasi ishlab chiqarish sohasining yanada takomillashishiga va global ehtiyojni qondirishga zamin yaratadi.

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